

Common Challenges Teachers Face in the Teaching of Literacy and Language in Multilingual Learning Contexts in Livingstone District, Zambia

Stephen Moyo ✉
The University of Zambia, Zambia

David Sani Mwanza
The University of Zambia, Zambia

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to assess the challenges faced by teachers with different levels of qualifications in teaching learners from multilingual learning contexts in primary schools of Livingstone District in Zambia. By adopting a qualitative approach, the study used a phenomenological research design on 3 teachers who were purposively sampled using maximum variation sampling technique. Interview guides were used to collect data from the teachers. The study found that the challenges teachers faced in teaching multilingual learning contexts including absenteeism, lack of teaching materials, language barriers, over-enrolment, and negative parental attitudes towards local languages. Irregular learner attendance hinders literacy progress, while inadequate multilingual resources compromise effective teaching. Language barriers arise when the language of instruction differs from learners' home languages, making comprehension difficult. Overcrowded classrooms, exacerbated by free education policies which limited teachers' ability to offer individualised attention. The study recommended that school administrators should tackle learner absenteeism through awareness campaigns, parent-teacher meetings, and support programs for struggling learners. Community engagement programs to sensitize parents about the importance of local languages in education and promote positive attitudes toward linguistic inclusivity.

Keywords: *levels of qualifications, managing multilingual learning, Livingstone District.*

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Introduction

Zambia is a culturally and linguistically diverse nation, home to 73 ethnic groups, each with its own language or dialect. English serves as the official language, predominantly used in governmental, business, and educational contexts (Banda and Mwanza, 2017). Additionally, seven Zambian languages namely Ibibemba, Silozi, Kiikaonde, Luvale, Cinyanja, Lunda, and Chitonga have been designated as regional official languages (MOE, 2013). These regional languages are employed as mediums of instruction from grades one to four, based on their prevalence in specific regions. For instance, Bemba is used in the Northern, Copperbelt, Luapula, and parts of Central and Muchinga Provinces, while Silozi predominates in the Western Province. Similarly, Chitonga is employed in the Southern Province, Cinyanja in Eastern and Lusaka Provinces, and Lunda, Luvale, and Kiikaonde in the North-Western Province (Banda, 2008 and Nyimbili, 2021).

Addressing literacy pedagogical challenges requires targeted professional development and training programs that equip teachers with the skills necessary to teach effectively in multilingual settings.

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Research highlights the effectiveness of such programs in improving learner outcomes. For instance, Mumba, Banda, and Chabalengula (2015) demonstrated that Zambian teachers who received specialized training in managing multilingual classrooms significantly improved their students' reading performance. These programs emphasise strategies such as differentiated instruction, culturally relevant teaching, and interactive learning, enabling teachers to navigate the complexities of multilingual education more effectively. Darling-Hammond (2000) and Goldhaber (2002) further affirm that well-prepared teachers are among the most critical school-related factors influencing student achievement. In multilingual settings, where linguistic diversity creates additional complexities, the importance of teacher competence is even more pronounced.

Lungu (2019) conducted a study to establish the effects of the use of Cinyanja as a medium of classroom instruction in selected primary schools in multilingual Chilanga district. The study employed a qualitative research design and Purposive and random sampling techniques were used to come up with 26 respondents. Data was collected through, interviews, document analysis, focus group discussions and classroom observations of literacy lessons. The study found that low reading levels were attributed to many other variables which include difficulties in the techniques used in the new literacy policy, Pupils absenteeism and lack of reading and learning materials the primary schools. It was also found that parents were not happy with the PLP language policy of using local languages as language of classroom instruction from grade one to four.

Mubanga and Musenge (2020) investigated the challenges teachers faced in the process of teaching reading phonic and sight words to fourth grade learners in the selected primary schools of Lusaka district Zambia. A questionnaire was administered to 100 learners who had just completed their fourth grade and another questionnaire to 20 fourth grade teachers in five primary schools. The study found that some children absconded themselves in the early days of their first grade (grade one) where early reading was introduced hence failed to cope up with reading Phonic and Sight words. The other challenge was over enrolment of pupils in the schools in the early grades because the government schools were few in the area hence teachers failed to pay attention to learners with learning difficulties due to the high pupil to teacher ratios.

The other challenges included lack of teaching and learning materials in the primary schools Nyimbili and Mwanza (2021) while Desta (2020) found that lack of teacher training, lack of materials, and unrelated educational qualification were major impediments of teachers while implementing teaching early reading. Meanwhile, Matsa, Moyo and Sibanda (2018) revealed that teachers and learners encountered a lot of challenges in the teaching of Ndebele cultural aspects because teachers lacked deeper knowledge of the Ndebele language and culturally rich instructional media to conduct effective lessons such multicultural classrooms. In addition, Simachenya (2016) argued that Livingstone is a multilingual town, and the classroom was not characterised by the use of Tonga. Nyimbili (2021) too stated that the classrooms of today are not corresponding to the zones which were created long time to enable teachers use zonal languages in Zambian schools. To this, Tembo and Nyimbili (2021) stated that the realised benefits of the use of Nsenga in the teaching to the Nsenga learners provided the learners with the practical understanding of the content the teacher was teaching about. The use of the community language in multilingual classes where the community language is not the language of instruction brings about learning in most Zambian schools.

Similarly, Sombonah, Ankrah & Korang (2024) study examined challenges experienced in the teaching and learning of English in a multilingual classroom's atmosphere, using the descriptive design. It took place at the Akrokeri College of Education in the Ashanti Region, Ghana. The study used a sample of 297 teachers and 67 teachers, using some sampling procedures. The study affirmed the existence of various challenges in the multilingual classroom, including weak linguistic background and learner anxiety. Based on these conclusions, the study recommended that teachers and students' use of English language, both in and outside the classrooms, be maximized since frequent use of the language increases its mastery, which is beneficial in the process of teaching and learning in the multilingual classrooms. It

is for this reason that the study will explore the availability of teaching and learning materials that cater for multilingual classrooms.

Another study by Chibesakunda & Mulenga (2019) establish views and investigate challenges faced by teachers and learners in the use of Ibibemba in teaching initial literacy in primary schools in Serenje district. A descriptive research design supported by qualitative data collection techniques was employed. The study found that the challenge of over enrolment of pupils in the schools in the early grades was common because the government schools were few in the area and this led to teachers failing to pay attention to learners with learning difficulties due to the high pupil to teacher ratios. It was also found that although the Ministry of General Education zoned Serenje district under Ibibemba instead of Ibilala in teaching initial literacy, learners' performance was low because the language used in school was unfamiliar to learners and there was lack of teacher's guide books and learners' text books to use in teaching initial literacy hence teacher's delivery of lessons was negatively affected. Therefore, the current study will explore ways by which teachers will enhance the in multilingual classrooms so that teachers can scale up their pedagogy for learners to benefit.

In addition, Kotira & Shizhou (2022) conducted a study to examine how the teaching challenges affect strategy use in second language classrooms in Tanzanian public primary schools, mainly in Manyara region. The 24 teachers from 46 teachers who teach Kiswahili and English languages of the three primary schools were randomly selected from Acronis, Engonongoi and Loorng'oswani located in Manyara region have been the participants of this research. The results of this study revealed that second language teaching in the classrooms faces different challenges in the use of strategies of teaching. Challenges that are found are overcrowded classroom, lack of teaching materials and teachers' poor knowledge on how students acquire second language. Therefore, the current study will explore teacher competence in multilingual classroom.

A study by Lungu and Mkandawire (2023) looked at the contribution of the physical environment to the teaching and learning of literacy skills among Grade Two pupils in selected primary schools of Lusaka District of Zambia. The targeted population was all primary schools, Grade Two pupils, and early grade teachers of Lusaka District. The sample size was four (4) primary schools and one hundred and twenty (120) Grade Two learners and thirty (30) primary school teachers handling early graders. Findings of the study revealed that the teaching and learning environment played a significant role on the teaching and learning of reading. Diverse factors in classes such as location of the school, print environment, class size, sitting arrangement, design of the class, and nature of materials contributed to the teaching and learning of literacy in the targeted schools. It was further established that parents in Lusaka district had a negative attitude towards the use of Chinyanja as a language of instruction because it was not the language of play, and it was not closer to the Chinyanja which the children used as a language of play. Ericsson (1993) argued that trained teachers possess intricate mental models of their field, facilitating rapid information processing and informed decision-making based on extensive experience. Teaching literacy needs critical decision making which should help learners in the classrooms.

Existing research on literacy skills in Zambia has predominantly focused on evaluating the literacy competences of learners across various educational levels (Matafwali, 2005; Matafwali, 2010; Zulu, 2019; Bwalya, 2019). While valuable insights have been gained from these studies, they largely emphasise learner performance without adequately addressing the role of teachers. A recent study by Mutolwa (2019) utilised interviews and document analysis to explore the preparedness of college lecturers in training teachers for literacy and language instruction. Njekwa and Nyimbili (2025) linked zonal language and linguistic oppression in the grade 1 classes. These studies have not linked teacher qualifications and multilingual contexts in the Zambia schools. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the challenges teachers of different levels of qualifications face in managing multilingual learning contexts in primary schools of Livingstone District.

The study answered the research question: what challenges teachers of different levels of qualifications face in managing multilingual learning contexts in primary schools of Livingstone District?

Methods and Materials

By adopting a qualitative approach, the study used a phenomenological research design to explore the challenges teachers of different levels of qualifications face in managing multilingual learning contexts in primary schools of Livingstone District. The study population included grade 1 teachers and learners in the primary schools of Livingstone town.

A sample of 3 teachers was purposively sampled using maximum variation sampling technique (Nyimbili & Nyimbili, 2024). This involved targeting a school which had three streams of grade 1 in the primary and these classes should be handled by different teachers of the same gender and different linguistic background. Furthermore, the teachers' qualifications were a critical factor in the selection process. The first teacher was required to hold both a diploma and a primary degree; the second teacher needed to possess only a primary diploma; and the third teacher had to have a primary diploma and a degree in any field. After thorough consideration, only one school met these specific criteria hence it was sampled.

Teacher X's highest qualification was a Bachelor in Primary Education. Teacher Y held a Diploma in Primary Education Teacher Z's highest qualification was a Bachelor in secondary Education -English Language and History. Interview guides were used to collect data from the teachers. The interviewed were conducted over a period of three months to ensure that the data being provided was consistent and relevant to the study. The bulky data which was provided was then coded and themes emerged from the data which were used to present the findings with. Key voices were documented to demonstrate data authenticity from each teacher using codes.

Findings

There were different challenges which different teachers faced in the process of teaching the multilingual learners in the primary schools of Livingstone district. These challenges are thematised under absenteeism, lack of multilingual related teaching materials, language barrier, over enrolment and parental attitude towards local languages in education and these have been used to present the discussion too.

Absenteeism

Teachers indicated challenges affecting the teaching of literacy in multilingual context were absenteeism. The participants established that a good number of learners could not break through to literacy due to inconsistency in attending literacy lessons. Through this, they lagged behind in the literacy lessons and failed to catch up in the process. Teacher X observed that:

I have realized that most of the learners miss lessons and by the time they would report to school they would have missed some sounds taught, hence, poor performance during assessments.

Teacher Z noted that:

The learners have not been coming to school regularly, which has made them fail to break through in the literacy lessons. Most of the learners are unable to read fluently. This is due to absenteeism and the environment the children come from.

Teacher Y also added that:

Absenteeism has been the main problem in the classrooms of today. You will find that more than 10 learners will be absent today and the next day a new set of pupils will be absent as well. This makes the teacher look as if he or she does not teach when it is the learners who are not present in Class.

Lack of Multilingual Related Teaching Materials

It was also established that there was a lack of multilingual related materials in the sampled schools and classes. The participants revealed that teaching and learning materials like pictures, objects and reference books were not available in schools to help in teaching literacy in the multilingual classrooms so that they could learn the sounds. Teacher X said:

There has been a lack of teaching and learning materials for us to teach literacy in this school. Materials like pupils' books and teachers' handbooks have not been received in this school apart from when the curriculum was launched.

Teacher Y said:

In this school, we have not received any teaching aid like charts, pictures, conversational posters and other wall posters to help us teach learners effectively. This has made us explain language concepts orally instead of showing learners.

Teacher Z stated that:

I have never seen materials being brought for literacy to support the teaching of this curriculum. The last time materials were brought was during the time it was introduced in 2014.

Language Barrier

The majority of the respondents indicated that failure of learners to understand the language of instruction affected the teaching of literacy in multilingual set up. This was also because the language of play for most children was not Tonga but Nyanja, Lozi and English to some of them who seemed to be the majority. For these children, they met the language of instruction in class and not at home or as they played. Teacher X said:

Most of the learners do not understand the local language of instruction and yet the teachers are busy explaining to them. The learners are not learning in this case while the teacher thinks they are learning. There is a need to use the language which learners understand for educational purposes.

Teacher Y stated:

The language issue is a reality in these Classes of today. Most of the learners do not understand the local language as they come from homes where they speak different languages therefore making it difficult to teach.

Teacher Z said:

The school is in a multilingual town, and we expect learners to have the knowledge of different languages which they speak in school. As a result, it is not easy to use Chitonga as a child's mother tongue/ medium of instruction.

Over Enrolment

The other challenge teachers faced in managing multilingual classrooms was that most schools were over enrolled, and teachers failed to give a one on one help to the learners remaining behind either through remedial work or just close guidance in the appropriate language. Here are the verbatim: Teacher X said:

Over enrolment is a big hindrance as it poses challenges in Class management as well as pupil attention during teaching is usually not enough. I have two streams to teach which big Classes are and this makes me tired. As a result, I cannot be effective.

Teacher Y stated that:

I have been failing even to make my learners respond in pairs, but I use group because there are many. This makes me fail to engage them in the language they can learn better as not everyone is able to respond to questions in class. This makes me fail to teach effectively.

Teacher Z said:

It is difficult for a teacher to do remedial work with slow learners due to over enrolment. Imagine a Class of more than eighty pupils and more than half cannot read and write, how can you provide individual assistance to such learners in Class, it is not possible.

Parental Attitude towards Local Languages/Education

Teachers also revealed that parents had a negative attitude towards the language of instruction because it was not their home language. Teachers also established that that some parents have a negative attitude towards Tonga which was not commonly used in the many families around the schools. Teacher X said:

The attitude of their parents towards education can also affect the teaching of literacy. When called to discuss the performance of their children, only a few usually come. Even when you start a conversation in a local language, the parents do not continue in most cases and tend to switch to English.

Teacher Y said:

The attitude of their parents towards education also contributes to the learners not performing well. Most parents do not support their children to learn in the local language. The children are not even helped with homework when it is in the local language.

Teacher Z said:

When we have a disciplinary case, some parents do not come to school after being called because they do not consider their children's education to be important. Fewer parents come when called and these are those who find education to be important.

Discussion of Findings

The participants established that a good number of learners could not break through to literacy due to inconsistency in attending literacy lessons and attendance in school. Through this, they lagged behind in the literacy lessons and failed to catch up in the process. The results of the study are in line Lungu (2019) who found that low reading levels were attributed to many other variables which include difficulties in the techniques used in the new literacy policy, Pupils absenteeism and lack of reading and learning materials the primary schools. Mubanga & Musenge (2020) too, support the findings when the study indicated that some children absconded themselves in the early days of their first grade (grade one) where early reading was introduced hence failed to cope up with reading Phonic and Sight words. Pupil absenteeism has affected learner achievements as they lag behind and the blame is shouldered on the teachers because of all learners have to perform better. From this, it should be stated that parents and teachers have to work together and help learners attend school if learners have to improve in the classroom. As much as we expect much from the teachers, there should collaborative efforts to support the learners in the classroom. It can also be argued that teacher poor performance is linked to the learner's absenteeism. Blaming teachers for learner's poor performance should be viewed from the angle of learner's lack of attendance. If this trend continues, we shall continue blaming teachers meanwhile it is the learners who creating this problem. Therefore, the expertism of the teachers in this case fails to bring about redemption and results after assessment. Teacher pedagogical knowledge and content application is mis judged in this context because they can only be effective if learners are attending lessons regularly.

The study also established that there was lack of multilingual related materials in the sampled schools and classes. The participants revealed that teaching and learning materials like pictures, objects and reference books were not available in schools to help in teaching literacy in the multilingual classrooms so that they could learn the sounds. The findings on lack of teaching and learning materials are in line with Nyimbili and Mwanza (2021) while Chibesakunda and Mulenga (2019) added that there was a lack of teacher's guide books and learners' text books to use in teaching initial literacy hence teacher's delivery of lessons was negatively affected. The findings were also supported by Desta (2020) who found that lack of teacher training, lack of materials, and unrelated educational qualification were major impediments of teachers while implementing teaching early reading. Meanwhile, Matsa, Moyo and Sibanda (2018) revealed that teachers and learners encountered a lot of challenges in the teaching of Ndebele cultural aspects because teachers lacked deeper knowledge of the Ndebele language and culturally rich instructional media to conduct effective lessons such multicultural classrooms. The lack of teaching and learning materials has been persisting in the different schools and countries and they have contributed to the poor performance of learners in literacy and language. The implication of this problem is that it makes teachers to be perceived as incompetent because they cannot deliver their lessons effectively using the right pedagogy. Also, they seem to look as if they have no content and yet it is the materials which are lacking for use in a given linguistic situation. This leads to teachers to deliver their lessons without relevant materials

thereby compromising the quality of education in the primary schools. Despite other sources claiming that teachers should be resourceful and innovative by making local teaching and learning material, there should be investment in material provision so that learners can learn using standard material instead of makeshifts which are not standard. This leads to compromising quality of education provision.

The findings of the study indicated that the language of instruction was not the language of play for most of the learners in the classrooms. It was also found that failure by learners to understand the language of instruction affected the teaching of literacy in multilingual set up. These results are supported by Simachenya (2016) who agreed that Livingstone is a multilingual town, and the classroom was not characterised by the use of Tonga. Nyimbili (2021) too stated that the classrooms of today are not corresponding to the zones which were created long time to enable teachers use zonal languages in Zambian schools. Further, Sombonah, Ankrah & Korang (2024) affirmed the existence of various challenges in the multilingual classroom, including weak linguistic background and learner anxiety. Chibesakunda & Mulenga (2019) also add that although the Ministry of General Education zoned Serenje district under Ibibemba instead of Icilala in teaching initial literacy, learners' performance was low because the language used in school was unfamiliar to learners. The language barrier revealed in this study was not exclusive to Livingstone district but to many Zambian schools because the classrooms of today are multilingual unlike what the policy makers seem to think of. Therefore, multilingual teaching approaches should be employed to enable the teachers break the barriers so that learners can learn effectively. The influence of language in teaching and learning is key because the teachers and learners use it as a medium of interaction within the lesson. Barriers in classroom communication results into learners failing to grasp the content of the subject matter despite the despite the teacher having the best pedagogies in the delivery of knowledge in classrooms.

The challenge teachers faced in teaching multilingual classrooms was that most schools were over enrolled, and teachers failed to give a one on one help to the learners remaining behind either through remedial work or just close guidance in the appropriate language. These findings are in line with Mubanga & Musenge (2020) who also found that the challenge of over enrolment of pupils in the schools in the early grades was common because the government schools were few in the area and this led to teachers failing to pay attention to learners with learning difficulties due to the high pupil to teacher ratios. Other scholars too have supported this finding like Kotira & Shizhou (2022) who found that challenges of overcrowded classroom, lack of teaching materials and teachers' poor knowledge on how students acquire second language to be a hindering factor to learner achievement in early literacy classes. The classrooms of today have become over crowded because the government has enhanced the free education policy by ensuring that every child attends school instead of being home due to school requirements. The teachers have come to find classroom spaces not enough especially in urban classes like Livingstone. This situation does not help teachers to ensure they help those lagging behind effectively because it becomes difficult to mark all the books and the work given becomes minimal. Therefore, the over enrolment becomes a challenge to the effective teaching of literacy in the Zambian multilingual schools which should be talked about. The implication of this is that the learners attend class yet their knowledge grasp is limited because they do not have access to the teacher for personal interaction. Due to large class, the teacher's pedagogical application cannot be effective because they need to deal with many learners at the sometime. Exhaustion and strength depletion becomes common hence they only attend to fast learners making the slow learners struggling. In this case, teacher knowledge cannot be assessed in such classes as there is a compromise of quality through the system. The teacher's expert in subject matter and knowledge sharing cannot be evaluated in this case.

The challenge established in this study was that parents had negative attitude towards the language of instruction because it was not their home language. It was also established that some parents have a negative attitude towards Chitonga which was not commonly used in the many families around the schools. The negative language attitude was confirmed by Lungu (2019) who found that parents were not happy with the PLP language policy of using local languages as language of classroom instruction from grade one to four. They preferred that their children to be taught the English language, they felt it was an official language for literate people as compared to an inferior language (Chinyanja). Lungu and

Mkandawire (2022) added that parents in Lusaka district had a negative attitude towards the use of Chinyanja as a language of instruction because it was not the language of play, and it was not closer to the Chinyanja which the children used as a language of play. Therefore, language attitude brings about a compromise on learner performance in the classrooms because the children tend not to consider the classroom language as an important language. The building of positive language attitude will bring about positive learning outcomes in the multilingual classrooms because all languages will be considered to be important.

The foregoing discussion on the challenges is in line with the expert theory by Ericsson (1993) following the principle of mental representation as a distinguishing feature of experts. He argues that trained teachers possess intricate mental models of their field, facilitating rapid information processing and informed decision-making based on extensive experience. For the teacher with well aligned qualification of a diploma and degree in primary education, it can be stated that if all teachers were to possess such qualifications, then the teaching of literacy would have less challenges in the Zambian primary school. Therefore, for teachers to teach literacy effectively in Zambia, they should have both the content and methodology from their training. This would then reduce the challenges which they are facing as a result of the lack of effective teacher training, and they would become experts in their field. The implication in this case is that the teachers are blamed for not displaying their content knowledge in the classroom meanwhile the system is made of different challenges which prevent their content delivery. Because of this, teachers being well trained and showing relevant experience in the classroom have been blamed for failing to help learners perform better in literacy. Positives in this case have to be considered because teachers are trying their best while the school and classroom factors are limiting the teachers to demonstrate their ability to show their content knowledge through the challenging system.

Conclusion

Teachers in Livingstone District face multiple challenges in managing multilingual learning contexts, including absenteeism, lack of teaching materials, language barriers, over-enrolment, and negative parental attitudes towards local languages. Irregular learner attendance hinders literacy progress, while inadequate multilingual resources compromise effective teaching. Language barriers arise when the language of instruction differs from learners' home languages, making comprehension difficult. Overcrowded classrooms, exacerbated by free education policies which limited teachers' ability to offer individualised attention. Additionally, some parents devalued local languages affecting learners' attitudes toward literacy instruction in local languages. The study highlights that despite the teachers' professional qualifications, effective learning in all classes remained elusive due to persistent challenges that hindered learning outcomes.

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